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Contested Integration in the Borderlands: Narrating the EU in German Regional Newspapers

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European integration is not only a political and economic process but also one of communication and contestation. This is especially visible in border regions, where the effects of European integration on borders are experienced most directly. This article examines how regional German newspapers on the border with Poland and Czechia construct narratives of Europe and bordering. Using qualitative media analysis, it shows that re-bordering is framed differently depending on the target of these measures, while regularly invoking the EU as a key frame of reference. The EU is narrated both positively as benefactor and protector, and critically through four ‘soft’ Eurosceptic narratives: two generic ones of EU distance and bureaucracy, and two highly localised ones centred on disappointment when the EU is seen not to live up to its own ideals, and on perceptions of European integration working less well in a Central European border region than in Western Europe. Rooted in controversies such as the Turów coal mine dispute or the disruptions of cross-border commuting during Covid-19, these narratives show that regional media not only replicate common criticisms but also produce place-specific ones. Taken together, the findings theorise border regions as sites where bordering events become narrative touchstones for evaluating EU performance and legitimacy.

Keywords: Narratives; Debordering; Re-bordering; European Union; Regional media; Border regions; Euroscepticism

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Introduction

European integration is not only a political and economic process but also one of communication and contestation. The European Union (EU) becomes visible in national and regional public spheres through the media, which serve as crucial intermediaries in narrating Europe to different publics (Trenz 2004; de Beus 2010).

This is particularly important in geographically and structurally peripheral border regions, where the EU's presence – or perceived absence – is experienced most directly (Paasi 1999; Newman 2006). While the EU has promoted cross-border mobility and cooperation through innovations like the Schengen Agreement and INTERREG funding, member states have often reasserted borders in response to crises such as the Covid-19 pandemic or concerns over migration from outside the EU (Wassenberg 2020; Weber & Wille 2020). These developments have resulted in complex narratives that reflect tensions between European integration and national sovereignty, and between openness and closure. In border regions, where everyday life is shaped by how open or closed the border is, local concerns are linked to supranational dynamics, including by regional media that frame European integration not as a distant polity but as a lived and contested process.

This article contributes to this special section on how Europe¹ is narrated and contested 'from below' (Schmidt 2009) through a case study of regional media on the German side of the Polish-

¹ In line with the source material analysed in this article, the term 'Europe' is used here as shorthand for the EU, reserving 'EU' for references to specific institutions, legal instruments, or competences.

Czech-German border region. Using qualitative media analysis, the article analyses narratives of bordering, the European Union and Euroscepticism in regional newspapers. The focus is explicitly on German-language media on the German side, consistent with the insight that, in the absence of a genuinely European or even transnational media landscape, media narratives are organised along national and linguistic lines (Koopmans & Statham 2010).

The analysis focuses on three interlinked themes: bordering, the EU as benefactor or disappointment, and Euroscepticism. The article proceeds as follows: the next section outlines the theoretical framework, drawing on the literatures on the narrative construction of Europe, Euroscepticism, and the special relevance of border regions to both. This is followed by a section on the data and methods. The analysis then shows that narratives frequently invoke Europe in stories of local crises or grievances, such as the Turów coal mine dispute or the disruption of cross-border commuting during Covid, casting the EU alternately as protector, benefactor, or failing guardian. Even when critical or disappointed, these narratives reveal that the EU is a key reference point in local narratives. The article concludes by reflecting on the implications for understanding the narrative construction of Europe in structurally peripheral border regions.

Narratives of Europe in Border Regions

The idea of Europe is contested and dynamic, and it is shaped through norms, ideas and narratives (Christiansen, Jørgensen & Wiener 1999, 532). Drawing on Anderson's (1991) seminal work on 'imagined communities', Delanty (1995) argues that Europe is 'invented' and sustained by narratives that emphasise its unity and common heritage. By invoking a sense of shared destiny, these narratives can serve to legitimise the political project that is the European

Union. However, such narratives are contested (De Vries 2023, 876) and can vary significantly across different countries and regions. And while some narratives may legitimise European integration, other, more critical, narratives do the opposite and voice disappointment or assign blame (Bürkner 2020; Bijsmans 2021).

Indeed, some critiques echo highly Eurosceptic narrative repertoires (Pfetsch & Heft 2015). Euroscepticism has been conceptualised as a broad set of critical stances on the EU, ranging from principled rejection to more issue-specific, ‘soft’ critiques and disillusionment with the effects of European integration (Szczerbiak & Taggart 2009). As noted in the introduction to this special section, Euroscepticism is not static: its manifestations are heterogeneous, and its intensity can vary across contexts and over time, particularly in response to events (see also Leconte 2010; De Wilde & Trenz 2012). In its ‘soft’ form in particular, Euroscepticism often takes on a contingent character, surfacing in response to concrete situations on the ground that are linked to EU-related rules and processes and that emerge from the perceived gaps between European promises and local realities (De Wilde & Trenz 2012; Bijsmans 2021).

Because Euroscepticism is dynamic and sensitive to events, moments of crisis such as the Euro crisis or the Covid-19 pandemic are a fertile ground for accounts that allocate blame or highlight policy failures (Weber & Wille 2020; Bijsmans 2021; Copeland & Maccaferri 2023). The media play a central role in shaping such narratives. Newspapers, in particular, have been investigated as key agents that produce meanings of Europe and that legitimise or challenge the European Union (Trenz 2004). The EU lacks a single media space. Instead, national and regional media are key intermediaries that translate EU-level developments into narratives that resonate with domestic publics in linguistically and politically structured public spheres (de Beus 2010; Risse 2010).

Narratives of Europe do not unfold in a vacuum but are shaped by specific places. This is especially true in structurally and geographically peripheral border regions, where the EU's presence – or perceived absence – is experienced as a practical manifestation of openness and cross-border linkages, rather than as an abstract political project (Newman 2006; Wassenberg 2020). In these spaces, the interaction between local, transnational and European developments is a fertile ground for often-contradictory narratives that are shaped by both routine cross-border practices as well as moments of conflict.

Thus, in border regions, the openness of borders becomes a touchstone for broader evaluations of the EU, for the very reason that European integration is experienced directly on the ground in these regions (Bürkner 2020): instances of debordering and re-bordering are easily narrated as evidence that integration is either delivering tangible benefits or failing to do so. *Debordering* means overcoming or softening borders, as exemplified in the Schengen Agreement that largely abolished border controls. In contrast, *re-bordering* means hardening previously soft borders, such as reassertions of national sovereignty during security crises (Popescu 2012; cf. Andreas 2003). Both processes can easily become objects of public narration, including in media coverage (Brambilla 2015; Newman 2006; van Houtum 2000). This is because they are not merely policy decisions on border management but discursive triggers: the media construct the meaning of borders in ways that link into European narratives (Balibar 2002; Brambilla 2015). Importantly, treating openness as a touchstone does not presume that these narratives will be uniformly positive: openness can be regarded as an opportunity or a threat, while closures may be presented as disruptive or protective, depending on the situation.

On this basis, border regions emerge as sites where the effects of European integration can be evaluated through its practical consequences. Because the EU is associated with facilitating cross-border mobility and cooperation, borderland narratives can cast the EU as a benefactor when openness is desired, but also as a disappointment when it is associated with undesirable externalities (Durand et al. 2020; cf. Nasr & Rieger 2024). Such evaluations feed into Eurosceptic narratives that take on ‘soft’ and contingent forms, expressed less as rejection of integration per se than as a criticism of EU rules or failures to protect border regions from negative outcomes (Szczerbiak & Taggart 2009; Leconte 2010).

This article therefore examines how bordering, EU performance, and contingent Euroscepticism are narrated in regional German media in the Polish-Czech-German border region. The German border region with Poland and Czechia is a useful setting for investigating how Europe and bordering are constructed in regional media narratives. As a structurally and geographically peripheral region, it offers valuable insights into how European integration is presented in local media narratives and shaped by place-specific histories and experiences (Newman 2006; Risse 2010; Kroll & Koschatzky 2020.). The border coincides with significant linguistic and institutional barriers, but it has also been the object of sustained EU-sponsored and bottom-up efforts at cross-border cooperation (Böhm et al. 2023). Local issues, such as a dispute over the Polish Turów coal mine or cross-border crime, as well as global disruptions like the Covid-19 pandemic, make this border region a useful case through which broader tensions between debordering and re-bordering and between supranational promise and perceived neglect become visible. The analysis traces how regional media negotiate the meanings of Europe through actual experiences of bordering practices.

Methods

This article employs a qualitative media analysis to examine how German regional newspapers on the border with Poland and Czechia construct narratives of Europe and bordering. Regional media offer a useful lens through which to trace these dynamics, as they articulate locally situated meanings of supranational processes and highlight the everyday implications of European integration. Drawing on theories of the narrative construction of Europe and Euroscepticism, the analysis focuses on how the EU is represented and contested within the structurally and geographically peripheral space that is the German part of the Polish-Czech-German border region. In practical terms, a narrative is defined as a recurring way of linking events to evaluations and expectations of the EU, including attributions of responsibility, expectations of EU action, and judgements of outcomes as beneficial or disappointing.

The empirical scope is confined to regional newspapers from the German side of the Polish-Czech-German border region. Throughout this paper, any references to this region are to the broader geographical context in which the German-language regional media are embedded. Two newspapers that cover Germany's southeastern border region with both Poland and Czechia were selected for their regional character and reporting, namely the *Sächsische Zeitung* (Saxon Newspaper) and the *Lausitzer Rundschau* (Lusatian Review). Both cover parts of the border region, with the *Lausitzer Rundschau* more focused on the Polish-German border and the *Sächsische Zeitung* covering the Saxon part of the Polish-Czech-German border region.

The *Lausitzer Rundschau* covers parts of Brandenburg and Saxony and is based in Cottbus. It has left-wing roots in the German Democratic Republic. Post-German unification, the *Lausitzer Rundschau* has won prizes for its critical reporting on right-wing radicalism in the region. Its circulation was approximately 50,000 in the fourth quarter of 2023 (IVW 2024a). The

Sächsische Zeitung, based in Dresden, covers (mostly eastern) Saxony and had a circulation of about 163,000 in the same period (IVW 2024b). Articles were accessed through the online archive on the Genios platform.

The timeframe covers the period between the 2019 and 2024 European elections. This period includes a number of significant events that featured prominently in regional and broader European media: the Covid-19 pandemic, the European election campaigns, the European Court of Justice's involvement in the Turów coal mine controversy and other localised events. These events were moments of salience that triggered media narratives about debordering and re-bordering, and their links to European integration.

Articles were collected from the Genios newspaper platform using a purposive sampling strategy. A set of keywords guided the search process, namely eurosceptic*,² border + Poland, border + Polish, border + Czech*, Brussels, EU.³ In total 140 articles that met these criteria were selected. 45 articles were selected from the *Lausitzer Rundschau* and 95 from the *Sächsische Zeitung*.⁴ Most of these articles are editorial reviews, opinion pieces and original articles.

² The asterisk means that any word starting with eurosceptic would be included among the results, including Euroscepticism, Eurosceptics and eurosceptical.

³ In the original German, these are: Euroskept*,³ Grenz* + Polen, Grenz + polnisch*, Grenz* + tschech*, Brüssel, EU.

⁴ The *Sächsische Zeitung* is overrepresented in this selection because it covered the Turów controversy more, which fit many of the search criteria (consistent with the purposive sampling).

The coding proceeded in two steps. First, all articles were imported into NVivo and coded using a small set of theoretically informed start codes aligned with the three analytical themes (debordering/re-bordering, EU performance, and Euroscepticism). Second, the coded material was re-read comparatively and supplemented with inductive codes capturing recurring case-specific storylines (e.g. Covid border closures and commuting, Turów, crime/trafficking, and an East-West contrast). Coding was conducted on the German-language originals, and all translations are the author's. As the approach was qualitative rather than quantitative, coding served primarily as a means of flagging themes, rather than measuring the frequency of certain themes. Accordingly, no code counts are reported, since the NVivo references should not be interpreted as comparable 'occurrences' across the dataset. Instead, the analysis distinguishes between recurrent and more occasional narrative patterns and substantiates each with multiple illustrations across outlets and years.

The analytical categories correspond to three higher-order narrative frames that were discussed in the theoretical section and used as start codes (bordering, EU performance, and Euroscepticism). Within these frames, the coding captures recurring smaller themes such as the EU as a benefactor, as a guardian of legal norms, as distant or overly bureaucratic, and as a disappointment in certain moments of crisis. The analysis also traces shifts between debordering and re-bordering narratives depending on the context (e.g. health crises as compared to environmental concerns) and examines how media representations link European themes to local experiences on the ground.

Analysis

Contested meanings of bordering and debordering

The first theme is that of re-bordering in a region where open borders had become the norm since Poland and Czechia joined the Schengen Area in 2007. The regional media do not portray openness or closure through a fixed perspective on debordering and re-bordering but rather frame borders situationally and pragmatically in response to specific triggers. Events such as the Covid-related border closures or an increase in irregular migration from third countries prompted very different frames, including a narrative of border closures as an exceptional and unacceptable departure from the norm, but also one of some border controls being necessary to enhance security. Some of these narratives are clustered around specific crises (e.g. Covid closures in 2020/21, migration in 2023), whereas others recur occasionally across the period covered (e.g. crime and policing), but all repeatedly raise the question of how the border should be governed.

In the Polish-Czech-German border region, as elsewhere, cross-border flows were disrupted by the Covid-related border closures, as noted in numerous newspaper articles, especially in 2020. One narrative portrayed Czech and particularly Polish enforcement as excessive, notably in cases where soldiers were involved in preventing border crossings (Lausitzer Rundschau 2020a, 10). However, opposition went beyond enforcement methods and extended to the very principle of re-bordering in response to Covid. This was despite the fact that Germany, which had closed its borders with other neighbouring states, avoided doing so with Poland and Czechia only because those countries closed their borders first. In what follows, it must be borne in mind that the decision to close the borders was taken at the national level.

The border closures were covered to a large extent through the issue of commuting, and the narrative in question was almost entirely devoted to the downsides of bordering. Cross-border

commuters faced quarantine rules and – in Saxony – mandatory testing at their own expense. Demonstrations calling for the border to be reopened were reported (Lausitzer Rundschau 2021a, 17), and employers highlighted their dependence on commuting workers. One article noted that ‘The Corona crisis ... shows how strongly the border regions have grown together’ (Sächsische Zeitung 2020a, 27). The German Chancellor Angela Merkel linked all this to the EU and was reported to criticise the closures as undermining the single market and European unity (Sächsische Zeitung 2020b, 18). A local company director was quoted as saying ‘I would not have imagined that such incalculable measures would happen within the EU’, and he concluded that the crisis had revealed ‘how dependent we all are on each other’ (Lausitzer Rundschau 2020b, 7). The media narrative surrounding border closures in response to Covid was overwhelmingly opposed to this form of re-bordering. This is because re-bordering undermined the open borders that had hitherto been taken for granted as a key aspect of European integration, as references to ‘European unity’ or the single market show. More than this, references to mutual dependence and border regions that have ‘grown together’ imply that open borders were taken as an implicit baseline against which the border closures were compared unfavourably. In this sense, Covid-related re-bordering was treated as a failure of the European level to protect open borders, even though specific re-bordering decisions were taken at the national level.

Narratives linking open borders to crime, particularly car theft, were more ambivalent. While careful to avoid stereotypes through the use of the passive voice and of neutral terms such as ‘the perpetrators’, the reporting established a connection between the end of border controls and crime: ‘After the abolition of border controls at the [border rivers] Oder and Neisse, the number of car thefts had shot up. This is because criminals, in contrast to police and prosecutors, who continue to be bound by judicial constraints, can exploit open borders in full for their own

ends. Berlin and Brandenburg were like self-service shops for them' (Lausitzer Rundschau 2019c, 16). Some politicians demanded night-time controls and a stronger police presence (Lausitzer Rundschau 2019e, 12). However, calls for re-bordering in response to theft were limited and muted, and there was much emphasis on other crime-fighting mechanisms such as cross-border police cooperation as well as technological solutions such as more cameras (Lausitzer Rundschau 2020d, 8). Openness, in other words, remained the reference point, and the narrative focused on how to govern its perceived risks.

Bordering returned as a major political theme in 2023 in response to a rise in irregular migration, and regional newspaper reporting relied heavily on citing politicians' positions. Saxony's Prime Minister Michael Kretschmer and other figures from his centre-right CDU party called for border controls at Germany's borders with Poland and Czechia. Kretschmer, who used the term 'avalanche' to describe the rise in illicit migration, said about the Polish and Czech borders that border controls were long overdue because more refugees crossed these borders than any of Germany's other borders: 'At the moment, migration is not steered by the EU or Germany but rather by criminal structures such as people smuggling organisations.' In his view, the government and Federal Police should carry out border controls (Sächsische Zeitung 2023a, 13). The new Görlitz district administrator Stephan Meyer (CDU) also cited the particular exposure of border districts (Sächsische Zeitung 2022c, 2). In contrast, the German government, specifically the Interior Minister Nancy Faeser from the centre-left SPD, stressed her desire to 'expand possibilities of domestic and cross-border cooperation'. To this end, she had reached an agreement with the Czech interior minister and representatives of the Polish Interior Ministry (Sächsische Zeitung 2023b, 15). As she later said, 'We need to fight irregular migration more strongly. But we need a lasting solution. That can only be achieved in Europe' (Sächsische

Zeitung 2023c, 2). Thus, while regional and local politicians disagreed with the government, both used the EU as a key reference point.

The examples of Covid, crime and migration show how support for or opposition to bordering is shaped not by consistent ideology, but by context and risk perception (cf. Côté-Boucher et al. 2014). They also vary depending on who is the target of re-bordering: Covid affected all residents, though above all commuters, but fortifying borders in response to crime or illegal immigration was presented as more targeted action aimed at people cast as outsiders. At the same time, debates about bordering are entangled with Europe because openness is widely treated as the normal condition of an internal EU border. Media narratives frequently reference the EU implicitly or explicitly as an institutional frame of expectation. Whether calling for open borders or effective migration policy, these stories reflect a belief that European integration should deliver tangible solutions for border regions. Debordering and re-bordering therefore function as a recurring test of the EU's performance and responsiveness in the borderlands. The next section examines how expectations of the EU as benefactor and protector alternate with more sceptical or disappointed narratives.

The EU as a benefactor and protector

As already shown, questions of bordering were repeatedly framed in reference to the EU. This implies an expectation for the EU to deliver. Indeed, the benefits of EU membership feature sporadically, but especially in 2024, on the 20-year anniversary of Poland's and Czechia's EU accession. Relatedly, there is a prevalent narrative that defines the EU as a protector. This is carried above all by Turów, which concentrates evaluations of the EU around law enforcement, but it also leaves room for disappointment when the EU is seen to fail in its duty as a protector.

As Faeser's comments cited above about a lasting solution to the migration crisis only being possible 'in Europe' make clear, 'Europe' and 'the EU' are used almost synonymously in German media. Since the EU has some competence in migration policy (Kriesi et al. 2021), Faeser's comment frames Germany's EU membership not merely as a potential solution but as the only possible framework for addressing cross-border migration challenges. Such statements frame the EU as a solution to domestic problems in an overarching narrative that casts it as a benefactor and protector.

One recurring narrative presents EU membership as beneficial for the border region. Local and regional politicians from Poland, Czechia and Germany were reported as praising the EU's support for cross-border cooperation: 'Without the EU, we wouldn't have many of the things we do today,' said the mayor of the Czech border town Hrádek, a sentiment echoed by then Görlitz district administrator Bernd Lange, who argued that the EU had moved the region 'from the periphery back to the centre of Europe' (Sächsische Zeitung 2019c, 15). This aligns with the position of Zittau's mayor Thomas Zenker, who, in the context of the Turów dispute, underscored the importance of upholding European law in border regions: 'I hope that we in the middle of Europe do not now have to watch how European law is no longer taken seriously thanks to bilateral negotiations and financial transfers. That would be the wrong signal for Europe and above all for the border regions' (Lausitzer Rundschau 2022c, 2).

The controversy over the Turów coal mine illustrates how the EU is invoked as a protector. The open-cast mine near the Polish town of Bogatynia, close to the German and Czech borders, was framed as a source of pollution and subsidence by German media, though also recognised as vital for Polish employment (Lausitzer Rundschau 2020e, 13; 2022c, 16; Sächsische Zeitung

2020c, 15; 2020d, 13; 2020e, 17; 2021b, 18; 2021c, 10). After Poland unilaterally extended its mining licence in 2020, the Czech government lodged a complaint with the European Commission, later escalating it to the European Court of Justice. The Court imposed a temporary halt and daily fines for non-compliance. However, in 2022, the Czech and Polish governments bypassed EU mechanisms and reached a bilateral agreement, in which Poland agreed to pay compensation and implement safeguards.

This sidelining of EU institutions in this bilateral deal prompted criticism on the German side. Zenker warned of a dangerous precedent for European law being ‘no longer taken seriously’ (Lausitzer Rundschau 2022c, 16). Media coverage often expressed more sympathy for Czech motives than for Saxony’s or Berlin’s passivity (Sächsische Zeitung 2021a, 13). The Turów case thus crystallised wider narratives about the EU’s role as a legal and environmental safeguard, but it also exposed the fragility of that role when institutions are circumvented or enforcement fails. The German media reports focused almost entirely on stories that criticised Turów and the exclusion of European institutions: the German MEP Anna Cavazzini was reported as highlighting the EU’s responsibility to protect citizens from cross-border harm, calling on the Commission to act on Turów (Sächsische Zeitung 2020c, 15), a view echoed by Greenpeace and other civil society actors (Sächsische Zeitung 2020d, 13). As also reported, a petition with 13,000 signatures demanded EU protection (Sächsische Zeitung 2020e, 17), and a broader declaration to European and national bodies condemned the mine’s environmental impact (Lausitzer Rundschau 2020e, 13). Thus, as the context evolved, narratives of the EU shifted from presenting it as a protector capable of delivering, to one in which the EU is easily undermined and ineffectual. In other words, in the very expectations of the EU there is also the seed of more sceptical narratives.

Finally, narratives of the benefits of the EU surfaced in more celebratory tones. Articles marking the twentieth anniversary of Poland's and Czechia's EU accession emphasised the practical and symbolic gains of joint membership (Sächsische Zeitung 2024a, 23). A Polish photographer in Görlitz recalled the disappearance of queues and bureaucratic hurdles (Sächsische Zeitung 2024b, 19), while the unfreezing of EU funds following a change of government in Warsaw was presented as an opportunity for regional renewal (Lausitzer Rundschau 2024a, 10).

To summarise, the three countries' EU membership is narrated periodically as both a viable solution to policy problems and as having everyday benefits at the border. This is the narrative of the EU as a benefactor. A related narrative of the EU as a protector is rooted above all in the Turów controversy, where it is linked to EU enforcement of environmental law. At the same time, the protector narrative is inherently fragile and can easily turn into one of a 'failed protector'. This leads into the next section, which outlines Eurosceptic narratives.

Eurosceptic narratives

Euroscepticism is a recurrent theme in Germany's border region with Czechia and Poland. This is first visible in party politics. For example, the Swiss journalist Peter Voegeli asked why Zittau, despite having benefited from EU membership, funding and open borders, remained a stronghold of the Eurosceptic, right-wing AfD party (Sächsische Zeitung 2020f, 16). The party gained electoral support across the border region and beyond, drawing sharp criticism from other German politicians (Sächsische Zeitung 2023d, 2). More broadly, there is concern about anti-EU, nativist voices. For example, the governor of the Czech Liberec Region Martin Puta warned that past traumas, such as war, border changes and forced population movements, could

be repeated if Eurosceptic alternatives gained ground: ‘The fact that we are now experiencing better times again is thanks to the EU’ (Sächsische Zeitung 2019c, 15).

Alongside concern about party-political Euroscepticism, the regional press reveals four broader narratives of disenchantment with the EU. Two of these – the perceived distance of the EU and its bureaucratic nature – are fairly typical Eurosceptic narratives, although they take on a local flavour. However, two others – namely the EU falling short of its own ideals in the region, and European integration working less well in this Central European border region than elsewhere in Western Europe – are examples of bottom-up Eurosceptic narratives in the region.

The first narrative is one of EU distance. The journalist Voegeli arrived at an answer to his question as to why the Eurosceptic AfD could be so successful in Zittau, which had benefited a lot from EU membership: ‘everyone in Zittau thinks Europe is good, but not the EU. And [Voegeli] also thinks he knows why this is so: because they feel forgotten and neglected here in the far east’ (Sächsische Zeitung 2020f, 16). This narrative was exemplified in an article that highlighted physical distance from decision makers but also a certain distance in terms of comprehension: ‘Almost exactly 868 kilometres lie between Cottbus and the administrative centre of the European Union in the Belgian capital Brussels. But it is not only these 868 kilometres of motorway that the people of Lusatia have to overcome if they want to achieve something for themselves at the EU headquarters and attract attention to their concerns’ (Lausitzer Rundschau 2019a, 6). The article continued to develop the distance narrative, which stressed the EU’s deputy director-general for energy, Klaus-Dieter Borchardt, getting an idea of local needs and in the process recognizing that his image of Lusatia needed to be updated.

The second narrative is a very prevalent one critiquing EU bureaucracy. Frustration with EU funding rules is part of this narrative. For example, Borchardt was quoted admitting that funding calls were too bureaucratic (Lausitzer Rundschau 2019a, 6). Other gripes included the fact that projects can only be funded between two countries, but not three, as shown in the example of an unsuccessful project for a bridge between the three countries – a project first floated when Poland and Czechia joined the EU in 2004: ‘We tried to bring in a pilot project with three equal partners. But the forms don't provide for that’ (Sächsische Zeitung 2022b, 9). Another example was the successful police cooperation project ‘Limes’ that was running out of funds until a new EU budget was approved. This was called a ‘scandal’ in regional reporting: ‘The car thieves will quickly realise when the pressure on them eases off’ (Lausitzer Rundschau 2019c, 16). This narrative implies that EU funds have created police cooperation that has put pressure on thieves, clearly identifying a positive impact. However, it is also implied that such cooperation requires some permanence rather than being affected by the bureaucracy of European budget cycles.

One article covered Polish farmers’ protests against EU agricultural policy that involved blocking border crossings. One such farmer was quoted as saying: ‘It is a catastrophe with the EU’ (Lausitzer Rundschau 2024b, 13), but the article did not elaborate in any greater depth on the reasons. There was also a related narrative about German farmers, who were said to feel pressure from EU regulations (Sächsische Zeitung 2024e, 14). In response to this criticism, the representative of the EU in Germany, Barbara Gessler, noted the need for a ‘strategic dialogue’ to ensure the financial security of farmers, while also taking into account environmental issues and global competition. She defended regulations but also admitted: ‘We are aware of the problems and have now presented a whole package of proposals to reduce the administrative burden on farms, especially smaller businesses, which may be burdened disproportionately. We

want to maintain more flexibility and reduce reporting requirements.’ (Sächsische Zeitung 2024e, 14). These concrete examples show that a general charge of EU bureaucracy is linked to many local examples of the negative effects of that bureaucracy. Indeed, even EU figures such as Borchardt or Gessler, were quoted as admitting that this bureaucracy can have localised negative effects.

A third, and periodically recurring, narrative is that of an elusive European ideal not being realised or being undermined. To some extent, this taps into the ‘EU as benefactor’ narrative, a pro-European conviction that EU membership would bring progress in many different policy areas. When this ideal is then starkly juxtaposed against reality on the ground, the result is disappointment. As already noted above, a director of a local company said about the Covid-related border closures: ‘I would not have imagined that such incalculable measures would happen within the EU’ (Lausitzer Rundschau 2020b, 7). Another example is that of Martin Puta implicitly equating EU membership with progress and being disappointed at the local cross-border rail infrastructure. He was quoted as saying: ‘It just can't be that 15 years after joining the EU, the tracks here are still so bad’ (Sächsische Zeitung 2019a, 14).

In 2022, a Czech teacher applied for a teaching job in Saxony, but faced considerable bureaucratic hurdles. The teacher was quoted as saying: ‘After 20 years of EU membership, do civil servants not know what the Polish and Czech certificates mean? We're not talking about Third World countries, we're talking about neighbours in the border triangle.’ The narrative stipulates that not only should the state of Saxony know about the teacher training systems in the neighbouring countries, but that it should do so because of joint EU membership. This failure, accordingly, came with penalties to Saxony, which urgently needed to recruit more teachers: ‘I know another colleague who came to Germany full of anticipation. But he didn't

bother with all these administrative procedures for long and is now working in the Czech Republic again' (Sächsische Zeitung 2022d, 17). Underpinning this narrative is the idea that joint EU membership should have led to easy free movement of workers – but failed to do so. The disappointment with a European ideal not realised is palpable here.

The fourth, and final, narrative, entails an unflattering contrast between the perceived reality of cross-border cooperation in Western Europe and that observed in a Central European border region. For example, the effects of the border closures at the Polish-German border were contrasted negatively with the experience at the Belgian-German-Dutch border, where there was a governmental task force, police cooperation and health cooperation: 'At the German-Polish border, similar consultations were almost unthinkable. The direct contacts between Brandenburg, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and Saxony with the neighbouring [Polish regions] proved not very resilient.' (Lausitzer Rundschau 2021a, 17). This is not necessarily attributed to a failure on the part of the EU but rather to the weakness of regional cooperative structures at the Polish-German border, compared to that observed at Germany's western borders:

Wherever there were agreements on cross-border health care and also on emergency services before Corona, but also stable regional coordination bodies, they have also stood the test in the pandemic,' says one scientist. For Brandenburg's border region with Poland, many such agreements are still missing. However, at least the offices of the Euroregions and the Frankfurt-Słubice Cooperation Centre, which runs a bilingual information hotline, have proved to be cooperative and citizen-oriented (Lausitzer Rundschau 2021a, 17).

In a 2021 article, a journalist described feelings of humiliation among Eastern Europeans that

resulted from the actions of big powers in the EU such as France and Germany: ‘They have the impression, not always wrongly, that they have been treated for decades as stubborn and economically and politically second-rate junior partners. As nations that have yet to learn democracy, civic community and the rule of law. Their unwillingness to adopt the Western value system in a way that they feel would make them mere clones of the West is growing louder’ (Sächsische Zeitung 2021d, 3).

It is worth quoting the subsequent analysis at some length:

In East Germany, too, in 1990 the principles and convictions of the West were transferred into a society that perceives itself to be colonised and devalued to a significant extent. ...

The fact that some in East Germany are still – perhaps again – embracing values that are sometimes different from traditionally western ones has been proven by countless studies. The acceptance of authoritarian ideas, the advocacy of a strong and maximally autonomous nation state, the rejection of the EU and liberalism, the desire for more isolation and dominant cultural homogeneity are more pronounced between the Baltic Sea and the Ore Mountains than between the North Sea and the Allgäu – Germany and our people first! Accordingly, the party that has these values on its blue flags could become strong here. It is no coincidence that Pegida⁵ emerged

⁵ Pegida (short for the German name ‘Patriotic Europeans Against the Islamisation of the Occident’) was a far-right movement that originated in Saxony. Active from 2014 until its

in the East, a movement whose content largely resembles an alternative to the Western canon of values, symbolised, among other things, by the copious use of the Russian flag (Sächsische Zeitung 2021d, 3).

In this narrative, East Germany is grouped with the other Central and Eastern European countries, which are presented as feeling misunderstood and hassled by patronising Western Europeans. Alongside examples of functioning instances of Western cross-border cooperation that are lacking at the Polish-Czech-German border, contrasts between Western Europe and Central and Eastern Europe are bound to be perceived unfavourably, linking this theme clearly to the Eurosceptic position that European integration works less well in the East.

Taken together, these narratives show that Euroscepticism in the regional media is of a ‘soft’ variety, which does not reject European integration as such, but which contests some of its effects on the ground. This takes both a general form by criticising EU distance and bureaucracy, but also a more contingent, local version that is linked to the specific context of the border region. In this sense, these narratives may go some way towards answering Voegeli’s question about why Eurosceptic parties such as the AfD have a stronghold in the region. One plausible answer is that the local effects of integration do not always satisfy the hopes pinned on the EU.

dissolution in 2024, the movement was known for organising demonstrations against Islam and against immigration.

Conclusion

This article has examined how regional German media on the German side of the Polish-Czech-German border region construct narratives of Europe and bordering 'from below'. Drawing on the literature on the narrative construction of Europe, it has shown how 'Europe' becomes a practical frame of reference in a borderland setting: bordering events repeatedly trigger attributions of responsibility, evaluations of EU performance, and, at times, contingent Eurosceptic narratives. Taken together, the findings point to a situational and locally grounded pattern of EU contestation.

First, the analysis revealed that narratives about bordering do not come from a fixed perspective but are highly dependent on the issue at stake. Thus, re-bordering in the shape of border closures during the Covid-19 pandemic was covered through highly critical media narratives that focused largely on the plight of commuters and the disruptions to everyday life in the border region. In contrast, re-bordering was presented in more favourable terms when the issues at stake were low-level crime and especially irregular migration. This supports the argument that border controls are a context-dependent practice that is framed in narratives by varying perceptions of risk (Côté-Boucher et al. 2014). These narratives shift depending on the issue, but they also differ depending on who the target is of re-bordering: when everybody is affected, as during Covid, then the narrative is highly critical; when bordering is aimed at perceived 'others' such as criminals or immigrants, it is more supportive.

Second, the EU appeared as a recurrent point of reference across diverse issue areas and was variously framed as a protector, as a benefactor or as distant and inadequate. Positive narratives highlighted European support for cross-border cooperation, general progress achieved through

European integration, and the EU's legal authority in environmental disputes such as that over the Turów coal mine. Precisely because these narratives raise expectations of the EU, they also contain the potential for disillusionment: when EU institutions are bypassed or seen as unable to enforce rules effectively, the protector frame can flip into one of a failed protector. The EU is thus presented both as capable of delivering, and as ineffectual, depending on the context. This implies that it is an actor whose legitimacy is conditional upon performance and perceived responsiveness, but which does not always live up to expectations.

Third, location emerged as central to how these narratives are developed. European integration is especially tangible in border regions, where cross-border commuting is a daily reality, where environmental harms transcend national boundaries, and where policy failures of coordination are felt most acutely. Border regions, therefore, function as places where the promises and limits of integration are especially visible. In the media reports analysed here, regional media linked these place-specific concerns – from commuting and policing to Turów and the frictions of funding rules – to supranational responsibilities and expectations. While this analytical focus cannot make any claims about how audiences receive these narratives, it does show how a peripheral borderland setting supplies recurring storylines through which Europe is rendered concrete but also contested.

Finally, Euroscepticism in the region emerged as a set of contingent narratives that are shaped by the EU's perceived shortcomings. Narratives of EU distance, bureaucracy, failure to live up to high expectations, and unequal integration combined generic Eurosceptic themes with borderland-specific frustrations but did not amount to a wholesale rejection of European integration. Underlying this soft Euroscepticism is a more integrationist, though sometimes disappointed, expectation that EU membership would bring unqualified progress. This aligns

with De Wilde and Trenz's (2012) argument that contestation is intrinsic to the evolving European polity, while specifying how, in a borderland setting, contestation is frequently anchored in concrete experiences of mobility, governance, and perceived neglect.

The analysis contributes to work that theorises border regions as sites where bordering events become narrative touchstones for evaluating EU performance. It is limited to media content and does not include audience reception. Future research could combine an analysis of how narratives are *constructed* with how they are *received* through a combination of media and audience research, and extend the design to Polish and Czech media to examine whether and how bordering experiences generate convergent or competing narratives across the whole border region.

To conclude, this paper has demonstrated that Europe is not merely a distant polity in regional media. It is negotiated through stories of bordering, cooperation, crisis, and conflict. The media narratives analysed here reflect an ongoing struggle to reconcile the ideals of European integration with the complex realities of its implementation. They offer insights into how European integration is experienced and narrated, showing that structurally peripheral border regions do not simply absorb EU narratives from the top down but also interpret and reframe them, sometimes in support, sometimes in criticism, from the bottom up. Recognising this bottom-up narrative work is crucial for understanding how Europe is imagined and contested in the everyday politics of border regions.

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